

STUDIES IN AROMATIC SULPHONYL CHLORIDES. PART III.
ACTION OF CHLOROSULPHONIC ACID ON TOLUENE
AND TOLUENESULPHONYL CHLORIDES.

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The reaction between toluene and chlorosulphonic acid has been systematically studied and that order of addition, i.e. addition of chlorosulphonic acid to toluene or toluene to chlorosulphonic acid, has been shown to exert a considerable influence on the formation of *o*- or *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride, and at higher temperatures the reaction becomes more complicated. Further action of chlorosulphonic acid on toluenesulphonyl chlorides has been investigated and it is found that it converts sulphonyl chlorides partly into soluble sulphonic acids and partly into di- and/or trisulphonyl chlorides. This conversion increases with the rise of temperature and the concentration of chlorosulphonic acid.

The acid chlorides of *o*- and *p*-toluenesulphonic acids are generally prepared by the action of chlorosulphonic acid on toluene, but very little information is found on the relative proportions of *o*- and *p*-isomers obtained under various conditions of temperature and concentration. Harding¹ carried out a few experiments in this direction and concluded that the local excess of toluene should be avoided to obtain maximum quantity of the *ortho*-isomer.

In the present paper a systematic attempt has been made to study the effect of temperature, relative proportions and order of addition of the reactants upon the yields of sulphonyl chlorides. Three different concentrations of toluene and chlorosulphonic acid (1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4 by mols.) have been used at temperatures ranging from 28° to 100°, and in all the cases the order of addition has also been reversed. The results are shown in Table I.

In the case of proportion 1 : 2, it has been found that total yield of the chlorides increases up to about 50° and the order of addition has negligible effect on the total yield (Table I). In agreement with the observation of Harding, the proportion of the *p*-isomer formed is much more in the case when chlorosulphonic acid is added to toluene. Above 50° the total yield of acid chlorides unexpectedly falls rapidly due probably to the further action of chlorosulphonic acid (*vide infra*), this effect being more pronounced when toluene is added to chlorosulphonic acid than that in the reverse case.

In the case of proportions 1 : 3 and 1 : 4, total yield of the acid chlorides at the same temperatures is greater, as would be expected, than that obtained when the proportion is 1 : 2. At higher temperatures the total yield decreases less rapidly than in the case of proportion 1 : 2. This is due to the formation of di- and/or trisulphonyl chlorides (*vide infra*). Continuous increase with rise of temperature in the yield of liquid product in Table IC, compared to Table IA, may be also due to this as much as to the formation of the *ortho*-isomer. Further, there is no appreciable change found in the total yield with rise of temperature when toluene is added to chlorosulphonic acid (Table IC), but in the reverse case, the total yield is maximum at 30° and it decreases with the rise of temperature up to about 70° (Table ID). In both the cases, the decomposition of acid chlorides by the action of chlorosulphonic acid and sulphuric acid, formed in the reaction, may be taking place; however, in the first case, on account of the large excess of chlorosulphonic acid present, dichloride formation is facilitated and this adds to the total yield.

The results obtained show that the action of chlorosulphonic acid on toluene is more complicated than that represented as :

The above results could only be explained on the assumption that under certain experimental conditions, a part of the monosulphonyl chlorides, initially formed, further reacts with chlorosulphonic acid to afford di- and/or trisulphonyl chloride and a part with excess chlorosulphonic acid and sulphuric acid, formed in the reaction, to furnish soluble sulphonic acids. To test this hypothesis the action of chlorosulphonic acid on sulphonyl chlorides has been systematically studied and the results are discussed below. Action of sulphuric acid on sulphonyl chlorides will be reported in the next communication.

A weighed quantity of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride was made to react with chlorosulphonic acid and the reaction mixture was poured into water. The insoluble solid and liquid sulphonyl chlorides were separated from soluble sulphonic acids. From the results (Table II) it appears that a part of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride is converted into water-soluble sulphonic acid and a part into *ortho*- and disulphonyl chlorides. The amount of conversion increases with the rise of temperature and the increase in concentration of chlorosulphonic acid. At 60°, the solid product recovered is unchanged *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride. From insoluble liquid product *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride was isolated and identified as its amide. In water-soluble products, the presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid was proved by its conversion into *s*-benzylthiuronium chloride derivative. At 80°, when the proportion of toluenesulphonyl chloride to chlorosulphonic acid is 1 : 2, some solid

unchanged *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride could be recovered; however, when the proportion is 1:3 or 1:4, no insoluble solid *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride could be recovered. The amount of *ortho*-isomer formed at this temperature was much more in all the cases than that at 60°, and it also increased with the increase of the amount of chlorosulphonic acid. The products of the reaction isolated are mainly *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid. As the amount of the *ortho*-isomer formed is large, it keeps some of the original *p*-isomer in solution. This is proved by converting the oily water-insoluble liquid into a mixture of amides wherefrom pure *p*-toluenesulphonamide³ (m.p. 136°) and *o*-toluenesulphonamide³ (m.p. 155-56°) are isolated. At 95°, the conversion of the chloride is nearly complete for all concentrations of chlorosulphonic acid. The insoluble material is much more than that in the previous cases and is proved to be a mixture of *o*-sulphonyl chloride, *p*-sulphonyl chloride and toluene-2:4-disulphonyl chloride, identified as the respective amides. The presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid was also detected. At 120°, the decomposition of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride is complete; however, the insoluble material, which is much less than that obtained under same conditions at 95°, is mainly toluene-2:4-disulphonyl chloride, identified as its amide⁴ (m.p. 187°). Soluble sulphonic acids are also detected.

Thus, the above experiments indicate that chlorosulphonic acid reacts with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride to furnish *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride and toluene-2:4-disulphonyl chloride and soluble sulphonic acids. In the presence of chlorosulphonic acid, sulphonyl chloride group of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride may migrate to *ortho*-position. Such a migration of sulphonic acid group in presence of sulphuric acid from *p*- to *o*-position is known.⁵ Further chlorosulphonic acid may react with sulphonyl chlorides to yield water-soluble sulphonic acids and sulphuryl chloride. In one experiment sulphuryl chloride was isolated and identified. The sulphonyl chlorides formed may further react with excess chlorosulphonic acid to afford di- and/or trisulphonyl chlorides. Sulphuric acid which would be a product of the reaction may also decompose *o*- or *p*-sulphonyl chloride to *o*- and *p*-sulphonic acids and di- and/or trisulphonyl chlorides into the corresponding sulphonic acids.

Similar experiments with *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride show that the decomposition of *o*-sulphonyl chloride increases with rise of temperature and increase in molecular proportion of chlorosulphonic acid. Compared to *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride, the conversion of *o*-sulphonyl chloride into toluene-2:4-disulphonyl chloride is easier. Even at 60°, disulphonyl chloride could be isolated as its amide; in the case of *p*-isomer, however, temperature as high as 95° is necessary. In addition to disulphonyl chloride, toluene-2:4:6-trisulphonyl chloride has been isolated as its amide from the experiments carried out at 80° and above, when chlorosulphonic acid is in

large excess. This compound could not be isolated by the action of chlorosulphonic acid on *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride even under drastic experimental conditions such as high temperature (140°) and high concentration of chlorosulphonic acid (1 : 7). 2 : 4-Disulphonyl chloride could not be converted into 2 : 4 : 6-trisulphonyl chloride by the action of chlorosulphonic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Order of addition of toluene and chlorosulphonic acid and its effect on the formation of toluenesulphonyl chlorides.—Toluene or chlorosulphonic acid (as the case may be) was taken in a three-necked flask, fitted with a rubber cork carrying a thermometer, a calcium chloride tube in one of the side necks and a separating funnel in the other. The flask was kept in a water-bath maintained at the required temperature. Toluene or chlorosulphonic acid was added from the separating funnel to chlorosulphonic acid or toluene. The addition was so adjusted that the temperature was never allowed to rise beyond the required range. The total time of the reaction was two hours. The flask was well shaken at intervals to ensure even mixing. After the required time the whole mixture was added to crushed ice. The substance separated was subjected to filtration when solid *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride remained on the filter paper and the liquid passed through along with the water. The solid was washed, dried in a desiccator and weighed. The liquid was then extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The liquid left after removal of the ether was then weighed. The results are shown in Table I.

Action of chlorosulphonic acid on p-toluenesulphonyl chloride.—A weighed quantity of dry sulphonyl chloride was taken in a test tube fitted with a rubber stopper and a calcium chloride tube, and a measured quantity of freshly distilled chlorosulphonic acid (*d* 1.78) was added to it. The test tube was heated in a suitable bath at the required temperature for a definite time. The whole mass was then poured over crushed ice in a fuming chamber. *p*-Sulphonyl chloride separated was filtered, dried and weighed. The filtrate was extracted with ether to remove a liquid or a semi-solid mass, and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the powdered mass was dried at 120°-130° for 2 to 3 hours. The dried mass was then shaken with chlorosulphonic acid and the mixture was poured on crushed ice. The solid that separated was filtered, washed and warmed with ammonia in a well corked stout bottle. The product was found to be identical with *p*-toluenesulphonamide from its m.p. and mixed m.p. with a pure sample.

s-Benzylthiuronium chloride is known to give crystalline salts with organic acids⁶. In one of the experiments, the filtrate after neutralisation was treated with solution of *s*-benzylthiuronium chloride and a crystalline

precipitate (m.p. 178°) was obtained. The melting point corresponds to the derivative of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I

Temp. of the reaction mixture.	Solid <i>p</i> -com-pound.	Liquid.	Total yield.	% of theory based on the formation of monochlorides.	Yield of isomers. <i>Para.</i>	<i>Ortho.</i>
A. Toluene (9.2 g.) was added to chlorosulphonic acid (23.2), the molecular proportion being 1 : 2. .						
28°-33°	6.3 g.	3.6 g.	9.9 g.	52.07	63.6%	30.4%
48°-53°	7.2	3.5	10.7	56.28	67.3	32.7
68°-73°	4.2	3.2	7.4	38.92	56.7	43.3
98°-103°	2.2	1.9	4.0	21.04	55	45
B. Chlorosulphonic acid was added to toluene, the mol. proportion being the same as in A. . .						
28°-33°	8.75	1.0	9.75	51.28	89.8	10.2
48°-53°	9.3	1.0	10.3	54.17	90.3	9.7
68°-73°	8.2	1.0	9.2	48.39	89.1	10.9
98°-103°	4.7	0.7	5.4	28.4	87.0	13.0
C. Toluene (9.2 g.) was added to chlorosulphonic acid (34.8 g.), the mol. proportion being 1 : 3.						
28°-33°	9.0	2.0	11.0	57.86%	81.81	18.19
48°-53°	7.5	4.0	11.4	60.49	65.22	34.78
68°-73°	6.5	4.75	11.25	59.20	51.7	42.3
98°-103°	5.5	5.0	10.5	55.20	52.3	47.62
D. Chlorosulphonic acid added to toluene, the mol. prop. being the same as in C.						
28°-33°	13.5	2.75	16.25	85.47	83.08	16.9
48°-53°	12.0	2.5	14.5	76.27	82.76	17.25
68°-73°	10.5	1.5	12.0	63.12	87.5	12.5
98°-103°	Pasty mass					
	12 g.		12.0	63.12	...	...
E. Toluene (9.2 g.) was added to chlorosulphonic acid (46.4 g.), the molecular proportion being 1 : 4.						
28°-33°	6.0	7.5	13.5	71.01	44.4	55.6
48°-53°	7.5	7.5	15.0	78.9	50.0	50.0
F. Chlorosulphonic acid was added to toluene, the mol. prop. being the same as in E.						
28°-33°	12.2	2.0	14.2	74.69	78.9	14.1
48°-53°	12.0	3.3	15.3	80.47	78.4	21.6

TABLE II

p-Sulphonyl chloride taken = 9.5 g.

	Temp.	Chloro-sulphonic acid.	Mol. prop.	Remaining solid <i>p</i> -sulphonyl chloride.	Quantity changed (total).	Liquid formed.	Product identified from the reaction mixture. ^a
1	60°	11.6 g.	1 : 2	7.3 g.	2.2 g.	0.3 g.	P+O+PS
2	60°	17.4	1 : 3	4.8	4.7	0.5	P+O+PS
3	60°	23.2	1 : 4	3.7	5.8	0.9	P+O+PS
4	80°	11.6	1 : 2	4.2	5.3	2.6	P+O+PS
5	80°	17.4	1 : 3	0.0	9.5	5.0	P+O+PS
6	80°	23.2	1 : 4	0.0	9.5	6.0	P+O+PS

The liquid obtained in the above experiments was shaken with liquor ammonia in a stoppered bottle and the solid formed was crystallised from alcohol (m.p. 155-56°), identified as *ortho*-toluenesulphonamide by mixed melting point with a genuine sample. This showed that the oil was mainly *o*-toluenesulphonyl chloride. When the liquid was cooled in ice a solid separated which was filtered. The solid and the liquid were then separately converted into their amides. The amide obtained from the solid on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 136°, and identified as *p*-toluenesulphonamide. The amide from the liquid melted at 155° and identified as *o*-toluenesulphonamide. Thus the liquid was a solution of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in *o*-sulphonyl chloride.

TABLE III

p-Sulphonyl chloride taken = 9.5 g.

Temp.	Chloro-sulphonic acid.	Mol. prop.	Remaining solid sulphonyl chloride.	Insoluble pasty mass.	Products identified from the reaction mixture.
95°	17.4 g.	1 : 3	Nil	5.3 g.	D+PS
95°	23.2	1 : 4	..	5.6	D+PS
120°	11.6	1 : 2	..	2.5	D+PS
120°	17.4	1 : 3	..	3.0	D+PS
120°	23.2	1 : 4	..	3.2	D+PS

P-*p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride.O-*o*-doP S-*p*-toluenesulphonic acid.

D-toluene-2 : 4-disulphonyl chloride.

O S-*o*-toluenesulphonic acid.

T-toluene-2 : 4 : 6-trisulphonyl chloride.

The pasty mass^b was warmed with liquor ammonia when an amide of m.p. 175-80° was obtained. On fractional crystallisation from alcohol the substance of m.p. 188° was obtained, which was identified as toluene-2 : 4 disulphonamide.

Table III also shows that with rise in temperature, the yield of the insoluble material is less. This may be due to the action of chlorosulphonic acid on disulphonyl chloride formed, and their further conversion into soluble sulphonic acids.

Action of chlorosulphonic acid on o-toluenesulphonyl chloride—Pure *o*-sulphonyl chloride was made to react with chlorosulphonic acid as described before. The reaction mixture after heating at a definite temperature for a definite period was poured over ice. It was filtered, the filtrate was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether was distilled. The residue was dried and weighed. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE IV

Temp. 60°. = Sulphonyl chloride taken = 9.5 g.

No.	Chlorosulphonic acid.	Mol. prop.	Reaction time.	Water-insoluble portion.	Products* identified.
1	11.6 g.	1 : 2	2 hrs.	5.6 g.	O+D+OS
2	17.4	1 : 3	4	6.2	O+D+OS
3	23.2	1 : 4	4	7.4	O+D+OS

TABLE V

Temp. = 80°. Sulphonyl chloride taken = 9.5 g.

Chlorosulphonic acid.	Mol. prop.	Water-insoluble portion.	Pasty solid.	Liquid.	Products* identified.
11.6 g.	1 : 2	9.2 g.	2.4 g.	6.8 g.	O+D+OS
17.4	1 : 3	7.2	5.6	1.6	O+D+OS
23.2	1 : 4	9.6	0	9.6	O+T+D+OS

In the first two experiments in Table V the reaction mixture was poured over ice and the insoluble portion was filtered when some pasty mass remained behind and the oily material passed with water. The pasty product and the oil were separately converted into amides, the former affording toluene-2 : 4-disulphonamide and the latter, *o*-toluenesulphonamide. In the third experiment the oily material obtained after ether extraction on keeping separated into a solid portion and a heavy liquid which was filtered. This liquid again separated into two layers. The upper layer was then separated from the lower heavier liquid. The pasty mass, the lighter liquid and the heavier liquid were separately converted into amides of m.p. 187°, 152° and 300° which corresponded to toluene-2 : 4-disulphonamide, *o*-toluenesulphonamide and toluene-2 : 4 : 6-trisulphonamide⁷.

TABLE VI

Temp. = 120°. Sulphonyl chloride = 9.5 g.

No.	Chlorosulphonic acid.	Mol. prop.	Water-insoluble portion.	Solid.	Liquid.	Product's identified*
1	11.6 g.	1 : 2	6.4	0.2 g.	6.0	D+T+OS
2	17.4	1 : 3	7.4	1.2	6.2	D+T+OS
3	23.2	1 : 4	10.0	3.0	7.0	D+T+OS

As in the previous experiments, the pasty mass and the oily material were separated and converted into amides. The pasty mass gave toluene-2:4-disulphonamide. The liquid gave a mixture of *o*-toluenesulphonamide and toluene 2:4:6-trisulphonamide which was separated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol into respective amides. Thus at higher temperature though di- and trisulphonyl chloride formation takes place, the amount of the water-insoluble material is rather low, indicating more conversion of sulphonyl chlorides into water-soluble sulphonic acids.

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